

WP 2650 – Measurement Suggestions

Measurements

- Soil albedo characterisation (once per site, not necessarily repeated)
- Below canopy PPFd measurements in all sites > distribution
- LAI measurements within the TA, spatially distributed to cover the whole area (as already kind of done for SP)
- Characterisation of the tower footprint

Data format

- API access to archive data
- Shapefile / Table with geometries for station data (including all SP, CP, and the TA). Currently not available and difficult to parse (see suggestion 3).
- Tower/instrument height information is important and should be easy to access if footprints are to be investigated.

Proposed structure

- 1) PPFd is easy to download and in a simply readable format.
 - a. Could have an associated geometry with it > to be discussed. E.g. ROI depending on the tower footprint.
- 2) LAI is not requestable through the API (custom code) and requires some modification, more usable format for satellite validation would be analogous to PPFd distribution.

Index	Date	Measurement plot	Measurement type	LAI

- 3) Plot information not requestable through API / not available on the website. Format (.kmz files) is not straightforward to parse. Usable format for satellite validation could be the following.

Index	Measurement plot	Geometry point	Geometry polygon